

EVIDENCE-BASED TOXICOLOGY
An open science journal for environmental health research

EBT Report (peer review round 1) for **TEBT-2024-0008**

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Submission Title	Systematic Review Methods in Environmental Health: a critical interpretive synthesis to inform the evolution of systematic review guidance
Submission Reference	TEBT-2024-0008
Handling Editor	Olwenn Martin ORCID: 0000-0003-2724-7882
Number of Reviewers	2
Submission Type	Single-Stage Study
Preprint DOI	10.5281/zenodo.11459414
Status	In Peer-Review
Evaluation Date	10 August 2024
Evaluation Round	Peer review round 1
Recommendation	Revise
Handling Editor's Explanation for Recommendation	Both reviewers agreed that this is an interesting manuscript reviewing guidance, manuals and frameworks for systematic reviews related to environmental health. Overall, it is clear and well-written. The first round of peer review did nonetheless stress that a few elements of the methods and results ought to be clarified.

Summary of reviewer comments

This manuscript presents the results of a systematic review of approaches, manuals and frameworks to conduct systematic reviews in environmental health. Fourteen frameworks were included in the critical interpretive synthesis and contributed new information to at least one of the themes grounded in the PRISMA framework. The first round of peer review stressed the importance of the research presented and agreed that findings may be useful to researchers who are selecting an approach for their review or developing resources to facilitate the uptake of systematic methods for reviews of environmental exposures. Both reviewers concurred that further details are needed to document methods and results more transparently.

Importance of impact of limitations on study findings	Overall, the only limitations identified were with the level of detail provided, particularly on methods and results. Addressing this will improve the usefulness of the manuscript to a wider audience but should only have limited impact on study findings.
Potential additional work to overcome limitations	Beyond editorial changes to add the required level of detail, there was a question regarding some of the categorisation decisions. Once reviewed, if the rationale is amended this would entail some additional reanalysis work.
Potential acceptability of characterising limitations instead of doing additional work	If a clear, transparent and reproducible rationale can be provided for categorisation decisions above, reanalysis would not be required.

Structured Assessment

1. Overall impressions of the manuscript

Editor's summary of reviewer comments and suggestions for responding

Both reviewers stressed the importance of the work presented in this manuscript. Equally both reviewers recommend that some sections, particularly those related to methods, be strengthened and to maximise the value of the research to other researchers in the field.

Reviewer comments

1. I think this is an interesting paper that can help researchers make sense of the many different frameworks for systematic reviews in environmental health. I think several sections of the paper could be clarified or strengthened.
2. This manuscript provides a useful review of the available manuals and frameworks for systematic reviews related to environmental health. The manuscript is well written and follows a clear and sensible structure. The manuscript is successful in achieving its aims and objectives however would benefit from increased transparency in its methodology - particularly around screening and data extraction. Overall, I believe this manuscript provides a useful contribution to the literature and will act as a useful resource for practitioners and researchers in the environmental health field and beyond, wanting to undertake a systematic review.

2. Are the research questions or knowledge goals important?

Editor's summary of reviewer comments and suggestions for responding

This has been addressed to much an extent in the previous section and both reviewers agreed on the importance of the knowledge goals. The only suggestion to improve the introduction section would be to explicitly state the aims and objectives and the review. Additionally, providing working definitions of the core concepts and principles will ensure the results are useful and accessible for as wide a readership as possible.

Reviewer comments

3. The authors have provided a clear justification for conducting the research and outlined the importance of this review to the field. It would be useful for the authors to more clearly state the aims and objectives of this review before going into the methodology. As noted by the editor, it would be useful if the authors provided their own definition and/or explanation of the core concepts of this review including what they consider a systematic review approach and environmental health. In general it would be good to see the authors speak more to the growing demand for systematic review and evidence synthesis in science and the emergence of different methods and approaches, whilst supporting this with evidence from the literature. This would strengthen the introduction and provide greater justification in the importance of this research.

3. Do the authors present a logical, rational, and/or plausible approach to achieving their research goals?

Editor's summary of reviewer comments and suggestions for responding

The approach to achieving research goals presented in the manuscript is through the critical interpretative analysis of information retrieved systematically. One of the reviewers raised the question as to whether this can be considered a systematic review or not. The answer to this question should become somewhat clearer once clarifications about methods (see section 4) have been provided. If all elements of a systematic review, including an explicitly stated research question and PI/ECO or other statement, are added to the manuscript, the abstract does not need to be amended. Otherwise, the method to retrieve literature should be referred to as a systematised search or other term that would more accurately describe the methods.

Reviewer comments

4. Pg 2: conclusion section of the abstract – I don't think you can call this a systematic review given the targeted searching that was conducted on agency websites? I prefer the term used in the title "critical interpretive synthesis." If this was a systematic review, what was your pre-stated research question?

4. Are the methods detailed and clear, with sufficient raw data and code to provide for transparency and potential reproducibility?

Editor's summary of reviewer comments and suggestions for responding

As previously mentioned, there is consensus between the reviewers and the handling editor that the methods section would benefit from a greater level of detail. Authors should carefully consider and address comments 5-21 on all steps of the methods from the research question to data synthesis via literature screening and data extraction.

Reviewer comments

5. Overall, this section of the manuscript would benefit from a greater level of detail to more clearly and transparently describe the methods to the reader.

6. The supplemental files are useful for transparently describing the search strategy and search strings. Information detailing the search dates, search number, results and who the search was performed by are listed for PUBMED and Cochrane but are missing for EMBASE. I do not have experience using EMBASE, therefore do not know if this information is accessible but suggest as much of this information is included for transparency. It would also be helpful if the authors could detail and/or label the columns (i.e, search number, search terms, search results). For consistency it would be useful if authors followed a similar template to that used in supplemental B.
7. Given this is a systematic review, it would be useful if the authors could provide clear inclusion/exclusion and/or eligibility criteria for texts at both the title and abstract and full text level. This would allow for greater transparency in the methodology. Whilst supplemental C lists the reasons for exclusion of frameworks excluded at full text it would be useful if the authors could provide a full list of the inclusion/exclusion in a separate file and note if the same criteria were used at the title and abstract level.
8. The authors note that screening and study selection was undertaken in duplicate, with disagreements resolved via discussion or by discussing a third reviewer. Please could the authors state in more detail the process for performing the screening in duplicate using the Covidence software and the process for overcoming disagreements (who was the third reviewer, what happens if reviewers could not come to an agreement, how was this process noted in the methods). It is good practice to screen in duplicate but it would be useful for the authors to note if any inter-rater reliability tests were used to assess level of agreement and if a minimum % agreement was considered sufficient (in case of disagreement). Cohen's Kappa coefficient is a commonly used statistical tool that the authors could use to measure inter-rater reliability and should be relatively simple to calculate post-hoc.
9. It is not clear at first if both reviewers screened 100% of texts or if one reviewer screened 100% and another screened a smaller %. Please clarify and more clearly state in the text the methods for screening / study selection.
10. The addition of the data extraction template in the supplemental material is good and aids the reader in understanding the thought process and detail that has gone into extraction. The authors note that the data extraction was piloted. It would be useful, and aid transparency if the data extraction table was included as supplemental material with some of the piloted information within it. This would help the reader see the formatting of the information when extracted from each framework.

11. Similar to the comments above - the authors note that the extraction and sampling of data was carried out by a single reviewer, with a second reviewer reviewing the data, and a third used to resolve disagreements. Please can the authors state what % of the extracted data the second reviewer assessed and to what extent the third reviewer was engaged to resolve disagreement. If there were disagreements, are the authors able to describe in the text or in the data table, where disagreements were present and how they were resolved.
12. The selection of the PRISMA foundation for an approach to data collection and sampling is good, however it would be useful if the authors provided more information on their choice of framework (in comparison to other approaches) and support this with evidence from the literature.
13. Pg 6, line 7: What do the authors mean by “until we reached a saturation of themes”? How can any of the following results (including descriptive results described in the next section) be representative if data were only collected until saturation?
14. The authors state that they purposively sampled eligible frameworks until they reached saturation of themes. It is not clear at this point in the manuscript what is meant by ‘saturation of themes’ and what they consider new and/or relevant information. This section implies that not all frameworks were sampled - please can the authors clarify what is meant here and provide more information in text, to more clearly explain the methods used. In addition it is not clear what the authors consider a PRISMA domain and/or theme. Table 4 is a useful presentation of how themes and domains are related, however more clarity could be provided in the text on what these are and how they were collated.
15. 13 PRISMA themes / domains are listed in the abstract whilst only 9 are studied in the text. Please can the authors ensure the abstract is aligned with the main body of the text or more clearly state which themes/domains are studied in the text.
16. There is also confusion here around the use of terminology - relating to the points made above, it is not clear what the difference between a PRISMA theme and domain is, or if in fact these terms are used interchangeably.
17. Pg 7, line 34-37: What were the criteria for including frameworks that were not specific to environmental health but were referenced as relevant approaches for SRs of environmental exposures? If these general frameworks were not part of the original search approach, how can the authors be certain that all relevant frameworks were captured here?
18. Pg 7, line 47-48: How was geographic location identified if there were authors from multiple countries?

19. The first paragraph of the data synthesis section is difficult to follow and lacks clarity of meaning. Please reformulate this section to more clearly state what synthesis occurred. For instance, it is not clear what examining the 'distribution of framework components or domains in relation to the characteristics of their developers, noting patterns in framework domain by type or setting of developer' means.
20. It would be useful if the authors could provide more information on their approach to data synthesis - in particular how they considered if a framework addressed each PRISMA domain, and whether an element and/or consideration of the framework was considered relevant. Similarly, what criteria were used to assess the similarities and/or differences between approaches. It would be useful if the authors could state whether these decisions were made by a single author or if more people were engaged in the decision making process.
21. Overall, this section of the manuscript would benefit from a greater level of detail to more clearly and transparently describe the author's approach to data synthesis and direct the reader to the relevant tables and supplemental material.

5. Are the authors' findings and conclusions justified given their data and methodological processes?

Editor's summary of reviewer comments and suggestions for responding

Similarly to methods, most reviewers comments are demands for sufficiently detailed information to understand the authors' results. There may also be a need to review the rationale for categorisation of some of the extracted information. Should the authors amend their approach to categorisation as a result, this would entail some additional work for reanalysis of the results. In any case, a clear, consistent and transparent rational for categorisation decisions should be provided to readers.

Reviewer comments

22. Given the review is complete and this is not a pre-print protocol it would be useful for the authors to provide the final extraction database in the form of an excel file. This would strengthen the manuscript and greatly aid the transparency of the methods and extracted data.

23. The presentation of the search results from the database and gray literature searches could be improved for simplicity. For instance, it is not at first clear that the 35 reports from manual search and 47 from citation exploration are those identified from the gray literature. It would be useful to list the total number of articles and reports from both database and grey literature searching individually and in total and highlight how many were removed via de-duplication. For instance, it is not clear (without looking at figure 1) why 3106 articles were screened when 3400+ were identified. The presentation of the search results, de-duplication and exclusion in figure 1 is good and the reader should be directed to this at the first point of mention. It would also be useful to note why articles could not / were not retrieved for screening.
24. I would advise the authors to detail the inclusion / exclusion information in a new paragraph. Like comments made above, it would be useful here to more clearly state the inclusion / exclusion criteria and list the number of articles excluded/included at both title and abstract, and full text levels. The reasons for exclusion listed could be better supported with quantitative data (i.e., % of articles excluded due to the report addressing scoping review methods). Again this is noted in figure 1 but should be incorporated into the main text.
25. When describing the selected frameworks (Description of characteristics) please include a full list of frameworks both in the text and in the supplemental material. It is not clear why only some of the selected frameworks are listed - if this is due to the subject focus then please clarify and point readers to a full list of included frameworks in table 2 at first point of mention.
26. It is not clear why you have chosen to collate the separate domains on 'study selection' and 'data extraction' into a single results section when treated individually elsewhere in the review. For consistency please either separate and discuss these sections individually or clearly state why they have been considered together.
27. Pg 7, line 13: What were the criteria to eliminate the 7 studies that were not included in the final 14 (from the 21 eligible frameworks)?
28. pg 10, line 30-31: Interesting finding regarding the approach to take the more conservative judgement. Suggest opening the sentence with a more general statement regarding the more common approach (consensus-based) and then pivoting to this alternative.
29. Pg. 12, first paragraph under "distinct systematic review considerations in environmental health" – this section seems to be framed from a clinical perspective and is missing the main reason that there are no clinical trials available in the environmental health field: the

nature of the environmental exposures themselves and our continued unconsented exposures. This paragraph should also emphasize the primacy of observational studies in environmental health.

30. Discussion section - this section could be strengthened by providing a discussion of strengths & weaknesses of different approaches.
31. pg. 14, Future Research section - please discuss future research needs regarding systematic review and evidence integration for mechanistic research
32. Table 1: it is unclear to me the difference between "toxicology and chemical safety" and "environmental health (general)". Are these topic areas provided by the authors of the SR frameworks or the authors of this manuscript?
33. Table 4: please check for completeness of the table. For example, under "systematic reviews should be considered following a prespecified protocol," it seems unlikely that the 2 references included are the only 2 that include that specification.
34. Table 5: Please check for completeness of the table. For example, I do not see EPA's method cited under "who's involved in protocol development." This table would be more effective/helpful to the community if it were complete. Also, some of the distinctions made between the entries create unnecessary distinction between the protocols. For example, Woodruff et al. suggests and "interdisciplinary team" for formulating the research question. I think something similar could be said for EPA 2022 – they should be subject matter experts and also multidisciplinary as relevant. Please review the table to ensure that the categories you are creating are not causing oversimplifications.

6. Other comments

35. Whenever the authors use an acronym (i.e., SR, EH) it would be helpful if they spelt out at first use and listed the acronym in brackets / parentheses to aid the reader.
36. There is inconsistency in terminology throughout the manuscript. This inevitably leads to confusion. Particularly when describing the frameworks, approaches and methodologies and the themes and domains. I would encourage the authors to choose a term and be consistent. Perhaps the addition of a glossary here would benefit the reader's understanding.
37. Table 1 - Please list the individual years for the final row '2015 and earlier'.
38. In general, all tables and supplemental material would benefit from a more detailed table or figure legend. This would better explain the data presented in the table / figure and air

reader understanding. For instance, in table 1 it is not clear what is meant by validation and in table 2 it is not clear if 'year' is year of first release, release studied in text or most recent version.

39. It would be useful for the authors to list the framework ID noted in table 3, in table 2 to aid read across, and understanding across data tables.
40. It would be useful if authors could provide a reference / DOI link to the framework in table 2. Given it is a systematic review and for transparency, it would be useful to the reader for authors to list the study and/or report in which each framework was identified. I think this would be a relatively simple addition to table 2 and would greatly benefit the presentation of results.
41. In the 'exclusion rationale' column of supplemental c the date range provided (2012-2023) does not align with that stated in text (2013-2023). Please amend for consistency.
42. Please direct the reader to the relevant supplemental material / table / figure at first point of mention.
43. Please provide a reference for the PICO/PECO framework.
44. It would be useful if the authors could upload their tables and supplemental material as separate files and consider the use of a repository such as the Open Science Framework.

Checklist of minimum required information

Y = Yes | N = No | X = Not Applicable

Present	Item checked
Y	Preprint, relevant revision materials, and supplemental material available on Zenodo
Y	Full name, affiliations, and ORCIDs (if available) of each author are present
Y	Structured abstract has been provided
Y	Author contributions in the form of a CRediT statement have been given
Y	Complete funding details are given, or "no funding" is declared
Y	An informative disclosure of interests for all authors has been provided, or disclosure declined
X	3rd-party data and program code are fully cited, if relevant (TOP 1, level 3)
X	Data and code availability has been stated and links to both are functional
Y	One or more appropriate reporting checklists for submission type have been completed

N

Supplemental materials have plain English file names

Comments about minimum required information

1. ORCID are given for some authors on ScholarOne but not on the manuscript file. It would also be useful to give addresses for co-authors' institutions.
2. Whilst there is a declaration of interests for all co-authors, at EBT we do encourage authors to complete a structured declaration of financial and non-financial interests. Only one co-author has used the template we offer (recommended but not required, [here](#)).
3. The supplementary information is included at the end of the manuscript, please save supplementary materials in separate files giving each file a plain English name.

Structured Evaluation

KEY: R = Revisions recommended. N = No issues identified at this time. X = Not applicable.

Domain	1. Objectives, context, and mode of research
Compliance	Moderate to minor issues identified that may be addressed after peer-review
Specific Issues	R Clarity about knowledge goals or hypotheses of the research (e.g. PECO) N Justification for conducting the research (context, rationale) N Differentiation between research in confirmatory or exploratory mode X Other (please explain in comments)
Comments	The justification for conducting the research is clearly exposed. The aim of the study is explained but could be clarified. To allow the reader to better understand the methodology, it would be worthwhile to expand on what is meant and define systematic review frameworks and approaches. This would allow the screening stage to become more transparent.

Domain	2. Soundness and rigour of experimental approach
Compliance	Moderate to minor issues identified that may be addressed after peer-review
Specific Issues	X Theory as to how the experiment delivers the knowledge goal R Identification and authentication of experimental components X Approach to power and replicates X Bias controls: e.g. randomisation, masking, complete data, training, etc. X Other (please explain in comments)

Comments	This is a systematic review. Although the protocol has been registered on PROSPERO, this process requires less information than a fully-fledged systematic review protocol. Whilst some elements of the SR methods are presented transparently (e.g.), others could be explained in more detail in the revised manuscript, particularly for the screening stage; eligibility criteria could be expanded upon, as well as information to clarify such criteria gleaned at the piloting of the screening stage if conducted.
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Domain	3. Analysis of data and reporting of results
Compliance	No issues identified during editorial review that should be addressed prior to peer-review
Specific Issues	X Data normalisation and cleansing techniques N Analysis pipeline (qualitative, narrative, and/or statistical methods) N Summarisation and visualisation of results N Selectivity in use of data or emphasis on study results X Other (please explain in comments)
Comments	Results are presented clearly and transparently and well supported by summary tables.

Domain	4. Transparency and reproducibility
Compliance	Moderate to minor issues identified that may be addressed after peer-review
Specific Issues	X Citation of data, program code, and methods (TOP 1 - L3)* R Provision of code, data, and materials for replication (TOP 2,3,4 - L2) N Appropriateness and/or implementation of reporting checklist (TOP 5 - L3) R Description of preregistered methods and/or analysis plan (TOP 6,7 – L2) R Adherence to preregistered methods and/or analysis plan (TOP 6,7 – L2) X Other (please explain in comments) *Parentheses indicate EBT's implementation of TOP guidelines. More information here.
Comments	Some further information on methods if available could be added to a revised manuscript to increase transparency and reproducibility. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. If available, bibliographic files of searches before and after screening could be provided as supplementary material. 2. A copy of the protocol registered on PROSPERO could be provided as supplementary material. 3. Desirable additional information about the screening stage has already been mentioned in Domain 2. Soundness and rigour of experimental approach. 4. If relevant, please document and comment on any deviations from planned methods.

Domain	5. Ethics and interests
Compliance	Moderate to minor issues identified that may be addressed after peer-review
Specific Issues	R Informativeness of declarations of interests X Ethical approval for research with human or animal material or participants X Other (please explain in comments)
Comments	Declarations of interest were provided but are rather brief. The use of our recommended template has already been mentioned in comments on minimum required information.